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Investigating the Readiness for Organizational Change: A Case Study from a Hotel Industry Context/Greece

Abstract

The main purpose of the current paper is to shed some light in the empirical gap of organizational readiness for change. For this reason, a quantitative research was designed. This research consisted of employees who work in Greek Hotel Companies. The tool used in the the current research was Readiness for Organizational Change Scale. This scale consists of 4 factors: appropriateness, management support, change efficacy, personally beneficial. The method used to analyse the connections between the aforementioned factors using factor analysis. The findings support the validity of Readiness Change Scale as a measurement tool for organizations established in the Greek hospitality industry. Hence, the current paper aims to contribute to the comprehension of the nature of readiness scale on the hospitality and tourism industry, and trigger future empirical research in the field, as there are only three published reviews which indicate measures of organizational readiness.

Keywords: *Readiness, Organizational Scale, Hotel Companies, Hospitality Industry, Measurement*

JEL Classification: Z32, L83, M10

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1. Introduction

One of the fundamental concepts of today's management is the change management. Actually, change management's importance has been highlighted due to the fact that the environment, where companies operate, is unstable and it has high levels of uncertainty. As an example the recent crisis of Covid-19 pandemic, has forced almost every company/organization on this planet to make changes; on some cases those were radical changes (Zaman et al., 2020).

A sector which has been affected by the recent events of the pandemic and also it is overall sensitive on any type of change that may happen on its macro-environment, is the tourist sector. Especially for Greece, the tourism industry is considered to be the backbone of the economy (Belias et al., 2022a,b, 2019a) which means that the Greek economy and regional development depends to a large extent on tourism (Tsiotas et al., 2020).

Greek tourism has already managed with great success several crises such as the financial crisis of the 2010's and the pandemic. The outcome is that the Greek tourist industry and its businesses have developed a resilience towards crises and an ability to change and adjust into post-crises environment, including the Covid-19 crisis. As a result, there is a rapid recovery for Greek tourism in 2022 where its arrivals may reach the pro-Covid19 figures (Papanikos, 2022). The ability of the Greek tourism industry to survive from two massive crises has also brought the need to investigate which are the key reasons that have resulted on this situation (Kousi et al., 2021). According to Belias et al. (2019b) but also to Day (2011), readiness for organizational change is a factor which may contribute to the ability of an organization to cope with a crisis. A recent publication made by Poulaki and Nikas (2021) indicates that tourists intent to return back to Greece partly because they feel that Greek tourism has made the necessary changes and adjustments so as to welcome tourists with safety. This is also an evidence that Greek tourist organizations have a high level of readiness to change, especially on major crises.

A crucial factor which will affect the readiness of the tourist industry to changes, is the employees' readiness for organizational change. There is a number of researchers which claim that overall the employees' readiness to change is a crucial factor for the success of organizational change (Asbari et al., 2020; Fadhilah et al., 2021; Zaman et al., 2020); this fact is even more crucial for the tourist sector, as stated by Awashti and Awashti (2022).

Despite of the fact that almost half of change management failures occur due to the lack of organizational readiness for change (Kotter in Weiner, 2020), there is still a lack of empirical data which will not only prove the above statement but also will establish the necessary research tool for the case of the Greek tourist sector and more precisely for the case of Greek employees on hotels. There have been some published reviews which indicate measures of organizational readiness (Gagnon et al., 2014; Holt et al., 2007; Weiner et al., 2008), but there is not any established tool for the case of the tourist sector. For this reason, the current paper is about to shed some light in the empirical gap of organizational readiness for change in the tourist sector, using the case of employees on five star hotels in Greece. The contribution of this paper is to examine the validity of the proposed research tool and to make suggestions for future research.

2. Literature Review

2.1. The Readiness For Organizational Change

The perception and the attitude of an organization's employees towards a change has been explored through both negative and positive perspectives. For example, those, who identify this attitude with a negative outlook, use terms such as resistance to change and dealing with change (e.g., Belias and Trihas, 2022a; Eby et al., 2000; Oreg and Berson, 2019; Piderit, 2000), while those who identify this attitude with a positive outlook, use terms such as

readiness for change, openness to change, receptivity to change, and adaptation to change (e.g., Blau and Peled, 2012; Belias and Trihas, 2022b).

From time to time various definitions have been given about readiness for change. For instance, Fixsen et al. (2009) claim that the term readiness for change defines the ability and willingness of an individual or an organization to engage in a particular activity. Holt (2000) identifies readiness for change as the degree to which an individual or group of individuals is mentally and emotionally willing to accept, embrace, and adopt a specific plan that will change a consolidated situation, a "status quo", as stated in his work. Also, Armenakis et al. (1993), consider the readiness of employees as the cognitive precursor of behavior to support the effort of change and its reflection in the willingness of the members of the organization to adopt this change. A common denominator of all the above definitions is that readiness for change is considered as a positive attitude of employees towards organizational change. According to Fixsen et al. (2009), readiness for change is not a pre-existing skill but can be developed and promoted. Holt (2000) considers the readiness for change as an integrated attitude that is simultaneously influenced by the content (i.e., what is going to change), the process (i.e., how the change is implemented), the environment (i.e., the conditions under which the change takes place) and the individuals (i.e., the characteristics of the individuals who have requested the change). Similarly, Armenakis et al. (1993) argue that readiness depends on the way its message is conveyed to employees.

Armenakis et al. (1999) have also claimed that in order for the message of change to be effective, it must include five issues such as divergence, self-sufficiency, personal strength, support and appropriateness. Studying, therefore, the factors presented by researchers that determine readiness for change could lead to the overall conclusion that readiness for change is related to the willingness of employees to initiate change and support it. Many authors have expressed, through research, the opinion that lack of readiness for change is one of the most important factors that hinder the introduction of change in an organization. For example, Armenakis et al. (1993) report that employees, depending on their readiness for change, facilitate or undermine the effectiveness of a change. In addition, Eby et al. (2000) argue that readiness for change is an insignificant factor in workers' resistance to large-scale change. Bernerth (2004), through the investigation of the role that readiness for change can play in the change process, argues that readiness for change creates the necessary positive energy for successful change support. So, it becomes clear that the readiness for change is a serious obstacle in the introduction of change, and the logical consequence of these researches is to look for the ways in which readiness for change will be created in an individual or in an organization. According to Applebaum and Wohl (2000), creating readiness for change is the active effort made by agents (in charge of change) so as to influence the beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors of change targets. As a result they would motivate them to change.

Armenakis et al. (1993) proposed a model of creating readiness for change that is related to how the message of change is conveyed. In addition, the analysis of the research made by Holt et al. (2007) showed that the readiness for change depended on whether the readiness was perceived as superficial (which means directed towards the processes and maintained the autonomy of employees and the power) or deeper (which means directed towards its structures and values).

On the case of tourism, organizational readiness has not been widely examined. An example is the pilot research made from Day (2011). The research produced the RCS (Readiness to Change Scale) scale which is a tool that calculates five variables related with the readiness of tourist organizations to deal with changes. Those scales are: the Precontemplation Scale, the Contemplation Scale, the Preparation Scale, the Action Scale and the Maintenance and Relapse Prevention Scale. RCS has been used on the case of examining the level of readiness of the personnel on Welsh hotels in order to cope with the changes brought as a result of the turn of the hospitality industry on sustainability. The outcome of this research was the fact that human resource training has a significant impact on the levels of

readiness in tourist sector. However, it seems that despite of the fact that Day's (2011) instrument of research had a high reliability score (Alpha Cronbach was more than 0.800 on all of the examined variables), it was not used on any other research. Similar researches have occurred from By and Daly (2008) and from Bondzi-Simpson and Ayeh (2019) but they did not manage to develop an instrument which can be used in order to calculate the readiness for organizational change in the tourist sector.

To sum up, it is understood that there is a gap in relation with the development of an instrument to measure organizational change in tourism. For this reason, there is the need to portray the instruments related with the readiness of organizational change.

2.2. Instruments For Measuring Readiness For Organizational Change

The tools for readiness for change have been firstly developed in the field of medicine and mainly in the field of psychiatry and psychology. More thoroughly, William & Tonigan (1997) developed a tool called SOCRATES that aims to assess the readiness and willingness of the patient (whom they call a client) to change. The tool consists of 19 elements with factors such as Recognition, Ambiguity, and Taking Action. According to William and Tonigan (1997) the readiness for a change of a patient significantly affects the patient in the search, monitoring and completion of a treatment. The researchers conclude that patient readiness for change is an important predictor of long-term treatment outcomes. Another example from the field of medicine is the Decision Balance Inventory of Brandenburg (Velicer et al., 1985). This tool assesses a person's readiness to change their diet and eating habits. More specifically, it assesses the readiness to make changes in a person's diet by measuring that person's perceptions of change about the pros and cons of diet. Brandenburg believes that people who have more advantages are better prepared for change. The readiness for change was also the subject of research in education. For this reason several tools have been created, such as the Receptivity to Change Inventory (RCI) originally developed by Hennigar (cited from Day, 2011) and Loup's Modified Receptivity to Change Inventory (1994), which was based on Hennigar's RCI. The MRCI, the RCI and other similar tools were developed to measure the overall readiness for organizational changes on various sectors such as medical and education sectors. However, those tools were not widely used (Gagnon et al., 2014); instead, there is a new wave of research instruments which rely on Holt et al. (2007) and it is considered as the most promising tool not only for measuring but also for understanding the readiness for organizational change (Gagnon et al., 2014; Weimer et al., 2008); hence, this research has used the Holt's instrument of research.

3. Methodology

3.1. Sampling and Data Collection

The research focused on employees who work on 5-star hotels. The researchers have distributed the questionnaire using the internet. More precisely, the questionnaire was developed in a digital form through Google Forms, where it was sent on employees who work on 5 Star Hotels all over Greece.

During the time of this research (April, 2022), there were 470 5-star hotels active based on data given by the Hellenic Chamber of Hotels (HHC). It is important to mention that the researchers have chosen 5-star hotels due to their size which allows them to rely on effective management as well as to apply best-practices regarding their human resource management.

The researchers received from HHC a list of the hotels which were operated at that time. They communicated with the HR department on all of the hotels which were on the list; where 23 hotels provided a positive feedback and they distributed the questionnaire to their employees. So, 593 questionnaires were sent to the employees. From the total of 593 questionnaires, 57 refused to answer, 115 did not answer at all (no response) and 49 did not answer correctly or they answered with missing values (more than the 50% of the total questions). As a result, 372 hotel employees answered the questionnaires. The locations of the

hotels where participants worked varied, with most hotels situated in Dodecanese (23.7%), Cyclades (16.7%), the Ionian Sea (13.4%), Chalcidice (12.4%), Thessaly and the Sporades Islands (7.5%), and Crete (6.5%).

3.2. Instrument of Research

As it was indicated on the previous chapter, Holt et al.'s (2007) questionnaire has been suggested by other researchers, such as Gagnon et al. (2014), as a reliable instrument of research; for this reason, the authors have decided to use this tool for the current research, since there is an empirical gap on this research field as also a lack of other instruments of research.

According to Holt et al. (2007), the idea of readiness originated in the context of efforts to avoid or address resistance to employee change. This is probably first mentioned by Coch and French (1948). Since the readiness for change began to be systematically studied, several tools have been developed to measure it. These tools are usually differentiated in terms of the factors that determine it, as well as in the total number of employees in which it was used to make the measurements. Readiness for change was used by the organizations in order to create organizational change; in medicine it was used with an emphasis on the cases of addicts. The research made by Holt et al. (2007) provides a fairly extensive review of tools for measuring readiness for change. In addition, it emphasizes on the content of each survey, the methodology used and the validity and reliability of these tools. One of the most well-structured tools for assessing readiness for change in an organization, is the tool of Holt et al. (2007). The authors used a sample of 900 people coming from both public and private sectors. Factor analysis is categorized into four factors. Those factors are the following:

- **Appropriateness of change:** It refers to the reasons that someone believes that there are legitimate causes or not for launching a change program
- **Management support:** It refers to the extent that someone has the feeling that the leadership and the upper management support and are committed (or not) to the change program
- **Change efficacy:** It refers to the belief that someone has, that he/she is able to implement the change program with success
- **Personally beneficial:** It refers to the extent that someone believes that the organization will benefit from this change (Holt et al., 2007).

Holt et al. (2007)'s instrument of research consists of twenty-five elements and is considered to be one of the most comprehensive in the field of organizational change as its construction required several tests to evaluate the internal consistency of the tool, the validity and the reliability of the sample. Participants expressed their level of agreement with each item using a 7-point response format ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 7 = strongly agree, as it is mentioned also on Holt et al. (2007). The authors translated the key statements of this questionnaire from English to Greece, in order to develop its Greek version. More thoroughly, in order to use the above research tool, the authors asked the permission from the creator of it (Holt, 2007). Holt et al. (2007) authorized the authors to use their tool for research purposes; so the authors followed all the seven steps that are methodologically required in order to apply the usage of a questionnaire which is created for a different language than the one that it will be used. According to Vallerand (in Banville Desrosiers and Genet-Volet, 2000) there are 7 steps that are required during the translation process in order for a translated questionnaire tool to be valid, accurate, reliable and similar meaning to the authentic questionnaire. These 7 steps are the following: a) preparation of preliminary versions, b) evaluation of preliminary versions and preparation of an experimental version, c) pretest of an experimental version, d) evaluation of the content and concurrent validity, e) reliability analysis, f) evaluation of the construct validity, and g) establishing norms. Each step is performed successively using a specific technique. After a step is finished, an assessment committee reviewed, evaluate and approved the results.

Finally, apart from the key items of the instrument of research, there were questions regarding the background of the participants, including demographic and professional questions.

3.3. Data Analysis

The aim of this research is the investigation of the reliability of the instrument of research. For this reason the internal consistency of the paper was examined by Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Regarding the method used to study the relationship between the factors, in this research, exploratory factor analysis was used. More precisely, exploratory factor analyses were performed for all scales and subscales of the questionnaire, so that their factor structure can be tested.

The study employed principal component analysis, and aimed to minimize data loss, by using primarily unrotated factor analytic models, or in some instances, Varimax rotation with Kaiser normalization. Additionally, measures of sampling adequacy (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) and sphericity (Bartlett's chi-square) were utilized in order to examine how well the data fit the factor analyses. Cronbach reliability tests for all scales and subscales as well as the factor analyses are reported in the next section. Finally, mean scores were calculated on all scales and subscales (presented in the Table 2).

4. Analysis and Results

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

Regarding the profile of the participants, the 97,8% had Greek nationality, the half of the sample were males (51.1%), while their age varied with 10.8% below 30 years, 28.5% between 31 and 40 years, 34.9% between 41 and 50 years, and with 25.8% aged over 50 years old. The educational background of participants also varied. More specifically, 21.5% had completed secondary education, 25.8% had gone to professional college, 17.2% had attended technological college, 16.1% had received a Bachelor's degree, 17.7% had received a Master's degree, and six participants had received a PhD degree (1.6%). The majority of participants were married (59.1%), with 29% being single and 11.8% being divorced.

As far as the professional background of the participants is concerned, half of the sample were permanently employed, while the other half were employed seasonally. A large proportion of the sample had work experience of over 20 years (43.5%); 17.7% had work experience of 16 to 20 years; 14% had experience between 11 to 15 years; 16.1% had experience of 6 to 10 years; and 8.6% had work experience up to 5 years. Participants' years of employment in the specific hotel varied between 1 to 2 years (15.1%), 3 to 5 years (20.4%), 6 to 10 years (24.2%), 10 to 20 years (20.4%), and over 20 years (19.9%) of working at the particular hotel.

The large proportion of the sample had been employed in the hotel industry in general for more than 5 years (overall 86%). Specifically, 3.2% had worked in the industry for 1 to 2 years, 10.8% had done so for 3 to 5 years, 25.3% had worked in the industry for 6 to 10 years, 26.3% had worked in the industry for 10 to 20 years, and 34.4% had been employed in the hotel industry for over 20 years. More information is given on Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic and work characteristics of the sample

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	190	51.1
	Female	182	48.9
Age	< 30	40	10.8
	31-40	106	28.5
	41-50	130	34.9

	> 50	96	25.8
Marital status	Single	108	29.0
	Married	220	59.1
	Divorced	44	11.8
Work experience (in years)	0-5	32	8.6
	6-10	60	16.1
	11-15	52	14.0
	16-20	66	17.7
	>20	162	43.5
Type of employment	Permanent position	186	50.0
	Seasonal position	186	50.0
Years of employment in the specific hotel unit	1-2	56	15.1
	3-5	76	20.4
	6-10	90	24.2
	10-20	76	20.4
	>20	74	19.9
Years of employment in the hotel industry	1-2	12	3.2
	3-5	40	10.8
	6-10	94	25.3
	10-20	98	26.3
	>20	128	34.4
Level of education	Secondary education	80	21.5
	Professional college	96	25.8
	Technological college	64	17.2
	Bachelor's Degree	60	16.1
	Master's Degree	66	17.7
	PhD Degree	6	1.6
Do you work in a 5 or 4 star hotel?	5 stars	182	48.9
	4 stars	190	51.1

4.2. Reliability, Mean Scores And Normality Of The Extracted Factors

The research has taken place in a sample of 372 employees on five star hotels in Greece. Table 2 presents the Cronbach reliability results for the scales and subscales, as well as the mean scores and normality results for the dimensions of the study. Additionally, reliability tests were computed for the overall scales of "Readiness for change". When the Cronbach's Alpha (α) values of the variables in the research are examined; the values were not found to be below than the threshold value of 0.60 (Hair et al., 2010). These values show that the internal consistency levels of the scales are quite reliable. More specifically, results showed that all dimensions of the study had acceptable Cronbach reliability, ranging from $\alpha = .67$ ("Appropriateness of change") to $\alpha = .92$ ("Personally beneficial"). In addition, Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests showed that the data does not follow the normal distribution ($p < .05$). Finally, the overall instrument of research that this paper used has an acceptable Cronbach reliability coefficient ($\alpha = .76$).

Table 2. Reliability of scales and subscales, mean scores and normality of dimensions of the study

SCALE ITEMS	Cronbach Alpha	Number of items	Mean	S.D	Kolmogorov-Smirnov*		
					Value	df	p
Readiness for change: 1. Appropriateness of change	.675	9	4.54	.678	.078	372	.000
Readiness for change: 2. Management support	.849	5	5.46	1.182	.122	372	.000
Readiness for change: 3. Change efficacy	.864	6	5.66	1.030	.099	372	.000
Readiness for change: 4. Personally beneficial	.912	3	2.66	1.517	.154	372	.000
Readiness for change Total	.764	25	4.67	.543	.074	372	.000

Table 2 provides evidence that the personnel of Greek hotels think that Greek hotels have a moderate level of readiness for organizational change. More precisely, the overall mean score was 4.67, which is a medium score. On the aspect of the variables of Readiness, employees believe their management is highly committed to change (management support), while the employees feel that they can implement a change process (change efficacy). On the contrary, the appropriate of change is not high, as they do not believe that they would have any benefit from a change that may happen on their workplace (personally beneficial).

4.3. Factor Analysis

For further analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling measurement, as suggested by Field (2000), was checked and as a result, each variable exceeded the 0.50 threshold level. More thoroughly, regarding the factors of Readiness for change, as shown in Table 2, the first factor analysis showed good data fit [KMO = .83, Bartlett's $\chi^2(45) = 1455.60$, $p < .0001$] and the initial model extracted two factors, which accounted for 59.84% of the observed variance (Table 3). An unrotated factor solution was selected, given that all rotated and unrotated models led to the exclusion of a single item out of the ten items: Item 7 - *When there are changes in the organization/in the hotel company, I perform my duties more easily* - was removed from analysis due to multicollinearity. The final model contained one factor, termed "Appropriateness of change", with 9 items out of ten initial items (Table 4).

The second analysis for Readiness for change had good data fit [KMO = .87, Bartlett's $\chi^2(15) = 1547.84$, $p < .0001$], and the model extracted one factor, "Management support", comprised of 5 items, and accounting for 64.79% of the observed variance (Table 3). An unrotated solution was therefore adopted. Item 15 - *When a change is to take place, employees spend a significant portion of their time, when top management, in essence, does not want it to happen* - was excluded from the analysis due to low loading to the factor (Table 4).

In the third factor analysis, data fit was good [KMO = .87, Bartlett's $\chi^2(15) = 1500.79$, $p < .0001$] and the model extracted one factor, "Change efficacy", accounting for 65.67% of observed variance (Table 3). All items were retained. Item 18 - *I believe that I will not be able*

to meet the new tasks that may arise as a result of changes in the organization - had a negative factor loading and was recoded in order to later calculate the specific dimension (Table 4). The fourth and final analysis for “Readiness for change” had good data fit [KMO = .75, Bartlett’s $\chi^2(3) = 770.31, p < .0001$] and the model extracted one factor, “Personally beneficial”, which explained 85.00% of the observed variance (Table 3). All items loaded into a single unrotated factor (Table 4). Finally, Table 4 and Figure 1 present the results for the four dimensions of “Readiness for change” in details.

Table 3. KMO and Bartlett’s tests for the four dimensions of “Readiness for change”

		Appropriateness of change	Management support	Change efficacy	Personally beneficial
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.83	.87	.87	.75
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approximate χ^2	1455.60	1547.84	1500.79	770.31
	df	45	15	15	3
	p	.000	.000	.000	.000

Table 4. Factor solution of four dimensions of “Readiness for change”

Factor	Items	Loadings
Readiness for change: Appropriateness of change	Item 1	.748
	Item 2	.717
	Item 3	.788
	Item 4	.799
	Item 5	.747
	Item 6	.845
	Item 8	.769
	Item 9	.700
	Item 10	.583
	Readiness for change: Management support	Item 11
Item 12		.930
Item 13		.906
Item 14		.846
Item 16		.774
Readiness for change: Change efficacy	Item 17	.753
	Item 18	-.447
	Item 19	.886
	Item 20	.913
	Item 21	.890
	Item 22	.872
Readiness for change: Personally beneficial	Item 23	.908
	Item 24	.920
	Item 25	.938

According to the below figure (Figure 1) all the loadings of every dimension of Readiness for Change are between .583 and .938 and they are statistically significant ($p < .0001$). In addition, Figure 1 shows the correlations between the four dimensions of Readiness for Change.

More specifically, Spearman coefficient values between .108 and .538 as well as between -.472 and -.710. As a result, the dimension Appropriateness of change is low correlated with the other three dimensions (Spearman coefficient .257 with Management support, .170 with Change efficacy and .108 with Personally beneficial). Besides, Figure 1 shows that there is a strong connection between Management support and Change efficacy (Spearman coefficient .538). Last but not least, there is a negative mediocre to very strong correlation between Personally beneficial and Management support and Change efficacy accordingly (Spearman coefficient -.472 with Management support and -.710 with Change efficacy).

Figure 1. Factor Analysis of four dimensions of Readiness For Change

5. Conclusion, Implications, and Limitations

The main purpose of the current paper is to shed some light in the empirical gap of organizational readiness for change and to evaluate a proposed research instrument which relied on the work of Holt et al. (2007). This scale consists of 4 factors: appropriateness, management support, change efficacy, personally beneficial. The method used to analyse the connections between the above factors was factor analysis.

The analysis of the responses shows that the hotel employees are ready to respond to a crisis in a moderate level. Overall, the hotel employees believe that their management is committed to the changes as well as they believe that they are able to implement those changes. Nonetheless, the appropriateness of the change is not always justified; as a result, they believe that they will not have any personal benefit from the changes. Therefore, this means that the management of the hotels will have to work more in order to help the personnel to understand the mechanisms of a change and also to find a personal beneficiary from those changes in order to motivate the employees.

Furthermore, the outcome of this research shows that the research instrument has an internal consistency of its factors as it was measured by Cronbach Alpha Coefficient test. Hence, there was an acceptable Cronbach reliability ($\alpha=.76$) also to the instrument of research as a whole. Regarding the factors of Readiness for change the factor analysis indicated the changes that have to be made for future research.

More specifically, as far as appropriateness is concerned factor analysis showed strong connections on all the items expect for item 7. Similarly, on management support, item 15 was excluded as it resulted low loading compared to the other five items. On the contrary, regarding the dimensions of change efficacy and personally beneficial, all the items of each dimension resulted high loadings; thus all these items were accepted.

Overall, the hospitality and tourism industry in Greece has been subject of at least two radical changes during the past 10 years (fiscal crisis and the Covid-19 pandemic); however, the tourism industry has managed to change and to adjust into the new realities (Belias et al., 2022a; Belias et al., 2022b), while it seems that 2022 can be the year where the tourism industry in Greece will fully recover from the pandemic. Nonetheless, it is useful for the hotel managers to be able to assess the readiness of his/her personnel so as to cope with an unexpected change.

For this reason, there is the need to establish a research instrument, as indicated on this paper, and to use it in order to help the sector to assess its readiness. Hence, a future research can use this questionnaire so as to assess the readiness for organizational change of the personnel on Greek hotels.

Although readiness for organizational change has been an important factor which concerns thousands of managers working on organizations worldwide, as it is already implied, there is a research gap concerning the implement of readiness tools into the hospitality and the tourism industry.

Some of the reasons that impede a hotel company from preparing its personnel to be ready for organizational change are the following: resilience for change context (Belias and Trihas, 2022c), lack of organizational learning culture (Viterouli et al., 2021) and disturbing organizational culture in general (Ntalakos et al., 2022a), lack of Human Resource Training as well as lack of Strategic Human Resource Management (Rossidis et al., 2021; Belias and Trihas, 2022d; Belias and Trihas, 2022e; Viterouli et al., 2022), Covid-19 crisis (Ntalakos et al., 2022b; Ntalakos et al., 2022c), lack of communication and lack of leadership (Ntalakos et al., 2022d; Ntalakos et al., 2022e; Zerva et al., 2022).

Hence, this paper contributes to the academics and practitioners by giving the appropriate measurement tool in order for a hotel company to be able to measure its employees' readiness for change. Also, the current paper aims to trigger future researches into applying this Holt et al. (2007) Readiness for organizational change tool, in order to have more generalized outcomes not only for Greece but also for hotel companies world-widely.

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Appendix

Questionnaire for Readiness for Change (Holt et al., 2007)	
Factors	Items
Readiness for change: Appropriateness of change	Item 1: “I think that the organization will benefit from this change”
	Item 2: “It doesn’t make much sense for us to initiate this change”
	Item 3: “There are legitimate reasons for us to make this change”
	Item 4: “This change will improve our organization’s overall efficiency”
	Item 5: “There are number of rational reasons for this change to be made”
	Item 6: “In the long run, I feel it will be worthwhile for me if the organization adopts this change”
	Item 7: “This change makes my job easier”
	Item 8: “When this change is implemented, I don’t believe there is anything for me to gain”
	Item 9: “The time we are spending on this change should be spent on something else”
	Item 10: “This change matches the priorities of our organization”
Readiness for change: Management Support	Item 11: “Our senior leaders have encouraged all of us to embrace this change”
	Item 12: “Our organization’s top decision makers have put all their support behind this change effort”
	Item 13: “Every senior manager has stressed the importance of this change”
	Item 14: “This organization’s most senior leader is committed to this change”
	Item 15: “I think we are spending a lot of time on this change when the senior managers don’t even want it implemented”
	Item 16: “Management has sent a clear signal this organization is going to change”
Readiness for change: Change Efficacy	Item 17: “I do not anticipate any problems adjusting to the work I will have when this change is adopted”
	Item 18: “There are some tasks that will be required when we change that I don’t think I can do well”
	Item 19: “When we implement this change, I feel I can handle it with ease”
	Item 20: “I have the skills that are needed to make this change work”
	Item 21: “When I set my mind to it, I can learn everything that will be required when

	this change is adopted”
	Item 22: “My past experiences make me confident that I will be able to perform successfully after this change is made”
Readiness for change: Personally Beneficial	Item 23: “I am worried I will lose some of my statues in this organization when this change is implemented”
	Item 24: “This change will disrupt many of the personal relationships I have developed”
	Item 25: “My future in this job will be limited because of this change”

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